

Racial Jokes on Twitter: A Pragmatic Study

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Abstract

Racial jokes are usually interpreted as one type of offensive joke. They are under-researched subject as opposed to the quickly expanding literatures about other kinds of racist language. The problem of the study is that English learners' potential lack of consciousness of such racially sensitive topic and how to concern with it within (online) intercultural interaction. As for aims, there is an attempt to investigate different aspects of racial jokes in "computer mediated communication" as well as to explore the interrelation between racial humor and the wide range of pragmatic strategies. Two hypotheses are established in this study, firstly, three types of racial jokes can be distinguished, i.e. these were incongruity resolution-based triggers, superiority-based triggers and blended triggers. Secondly, most racial jokes are concerned with incongruity-based triggers. The data is limited to (3) racial jokes (one joke for each type) collected from different racial joke accounts on Twitter. The current study follows qualitative method. From a conceptual viewpoint, it will also depend on Attardo and Raskin's Theory of Humor (2017). To apply its aims and verify its hypotheses, the study maintains the following steps:

1. *Re-visiting the literature on the concept of racial joke, implicature and Grice's maxims.*
2. *Collecting sufficient amount of the data in question from the Twitter.*
3. *Analyzing the data qualitatively for the purpose of identifying forms of racial jokes online.*
4. *Providing the result based on the analysis.*

Introduction

The current section deals with the racial jokes, which can be merely described as the tendency to provide amusement and provoke laughter. It will introduce various definitions from different viewpoints, mentioning an explanation of theories of humor, i.e. incongruity resolution theories, relief theories and superiority theories. It will also discuss the concept of humor in relation to pragmatic issues, i.e. implicature and Grice's maxims.

1.1.1 Concept of Racial Joke

Ritchie (2004:15) describes a joke as "a relatively brief text that, for a certain cultural association its basic purpose, the performing of a distracted reaction within its readers/hearers, and that is usually repeatable in widespread range of conditions". Within the scope of linguistics, "jokes" make usage of linguistic vagueness and there becomes an aspect of jokes which recognizes themselves not by actions or happenings, but relied on special linguistic properties or features of language for their impact. A special form of jokes can be considered as highly "language-dependent". Such aspect of jokes is widely known as "pun", (Zabalbeascoa, 1996:253).

From genre attitude, jokes involve special textual, linguistic and functional features. Attardo (2001: 61-62) assumes that jokes can often be described as easy together, brief as well as painful stories that are reported for the purpose of amusing addressers. He (ibid) differentiates two kinds of jokes that are canned/narrative and conversational jokes. Narrative jokes/canned jokes are often reported by narrators who suggest that jokes within the announcement of the humorous nature of the forthcoming turns. These jokes are "rehearsed" i.e., it can be heard or made by the narrators before telling. They are also normally split from the situation by which they are told. Alternatively, "interactional jokes" can be informed as if ordered parts in interaction, without prefixing. These jokes can be performed by tellers and are so context-dependent.

Moreover, Shade (1994:3) illustrates that there are certain jokes which can be anything performed to provoke funny attitudes, but they have to involve certain traits, such as: different senses of idioms, metaphors and words; vague; unpredicted and incongruity shift of perspectives.

A special kind of jokes is called "racial jokes". They have, actually, a long history, particularly in the United States. On this occasion, Willis (2005:131) and

Billings(2005:31)statethatsuch jokeshaveservedboth"anoppressiveandupliftingelement"for racial minority associations. In terms of social productions, jokes depend heavily oncontext for failure or success. Whoever laughs at racial jokes often relies on who is reporting them. It has been claimed that appropriate laughter at ethnic jokes is contingentuponaningroupmemberstellingit,so as toacknowledgethatthereare features within which the jokesare beingtold.

Hughes (2003: 1443) views that during the 19th century racial jokes had two basic social functions. Firstly, "the flurryof jokes"which targetednewlyreachedimmigrantassociationsshowedtheregardof"white Americans" that they could collapse their privileged social positions. Such jokes usually described immigrants as stupid,lazy or dirty, and focused on their inalterable divergences. Secondly, racial jokes also highlighted on the current social considerations. For instance, during "Industrial Revolution", entrepreneurs passed by constantly growing with the furious paces of technology.

The racial jokes are typically employed as effective devices of social effects, which enhance not solely scalewithin societies but also social orders.Thefeelingsofsociallinksismostlyreflectedin terms ofother individuals of the social associations, in which a special social status is stated. Tellingracialjokesalsoworksasaspectsofexpressingfeelings,moods, attitudes and perspectives on certain social facts, with the goals of evolving in-group relationships, mitigate tensions among individuals of the identical association, solidarity and enhance self-identification. Moreover, maladaptive humour styles such as: jokes, sarcasm or irony and hostile/offensive areoftenemployedtoridiculeandcontemptindividualsoftherracialassociations which are regarded as inferior. This denotes that racial jokes may have serious affective, social andmoralimpactsontheinteractionsbywhichtheyareutilized, (Herring, 2004: 338).

Social media can be utilized to circulate and produce humorous texts, as in, jokes. Certainly, the production and circulating such jokes via computer technologyprimarilyhappensbymeansoflanguage,buttthey canalsomakeusageof visual signs as well. Social media employers often communicate in terms of verbal language, as they usually read just like texts and print within keyboards on computerscreens.

Such effort is facilitated by the fact that people engage in socially meaningful, involving activities, humorous online in ways that usually leave textual traces, (Herring, 2004: 338). Circulating and posting racial jokes on social media are heavily influenced by the medium and situational affordancesuppliedbytheonlineplatformemployed.Suchaffordancesmaynot solely influence how these jokes are circulated and posted but, more crucially, how they are made and interpreted within online context, (ibid).

1.1.2 Theories of VerbalHumor

Three humor theories can be distinguished, i.e.superiority, relief and incongruity-based triggers. They will be illustrated as follows:

- **Superiority Theory**

Superiority theory deals with thenotion that laughters express feelings of superiority over other individuals or over formers state of themselves. A remarkable pioneer of the current theory is called "Roger Scruton", who investigates amusementasan"attentivedemolition"ofanindividualorsomethingjoinedwith individuals. "If people dislike being laughed at..... It is certainly because laughter lessens its object in the subject's eyes", (Scruton, 1986: 156). Besides, Morreal(1983:4)indicates that"theSuperiorityTheory"isonetheprimary andfamoushumortheory.Basedonthistheory,humourcanbecounted asutterances of individuals' feelings of superiority over others. From historical viewpoint, Morreal makes it clear that "superiority theory" belongs to Plato, (427-347 BC), who stated that the tasks of humour originates from the wicked and foolish nature of humans. Plato thought that self-ignorance refers to what an individual laughable.

Berger (1987: 8) mentions that:

"Humor from the superiority theorists, is always social or cultural and always involves comparisons of invidious natureSuperioritytheorydoesnotonlyrefertotheinclusionofshortcomings in others as an essential aspect of humor, butit also illuminates the mixture social relations and cultural perspectives through the usage of jokes".

To sum up, superiority theory of humour is more interested in "racist and dodgy ethnic jokes, sexist jokes, mother-in-law jokes and all those types of politically incorrect jokes" (Jensen, 2009:8).

- **ReliefTheory**

Hu (2012: 78) postulates that the "Relief Theory of Humor" can be comprehended from a psychological view. It denotes that humour is a kind of "relief from social pressure, both psychological and physical". Based on "Relief Theory", humour may be used to make senses relief from negative stresses and emotions. Topics deemed as a taboo in communities (i.e. sex, death, religion, etc.) or those that concern with matter not normally thought being funny, i.e., historical events like the holocaust, 9/11, form the basic topics of the relief-based humor expression.

The two most well-known relief theorists are Sigmund Freud and Herbert Spencer. As for versions of this theory, they can be distinguished:

- The strong version affirms that a release of excessive energy leads to laughter.
- The weak version affirms that humor's laughter involves a release of tension or energy.

Based on "Release Theory of Humor", individuals make humor since they suggest that pressure is condensed by performing so, (Azeez and Turki, 2019: 14). Finally, Hurley, et al. (2011: 44-45) outlines that release theories of humor consider humor as a relief from redundant nervous arousal. Thus, release theories maintain that tension build up may be freed by favorable emotions that based on further thoughts, the power is alternated into laughing.

- **Incongruity Resolution Theory**

As far as incongruity resolution is concerned, it can be viewed through shifting the senses of the source from the commonsenses to a novel and unexpected ones, (Steen, 2007: 280). Thus, the salient senses of expressions, phrases or utterances may be abandoned in favor of implicit and unpredicted but appropriate ones. On this occasion, Marin-Arrese (2008: 4) points out that "incongruity" can be counted as a clash between the frequent, direct interpretative meaning and a shift, unpopular and more implicit sense that leads to the re-comprehension of the funny utterances. Particularly, incongruity grows from the flouting of the speech expectation, absence of coherence, emotion of tension, co-existence of two clashing notions, or frames of source, forming a mismatch between the predicted contents and real utterances, (Miller, 2009:3).

The earlier version of "incongruity resolution theory" of humor was first suggested by Aristotle, (Morreal, 1983: 16). Aristotle counts humor as "a method through which speakers have capacity to create laughter, by leading the addressees to form specific expectations before amusing them with conclusions they cannot expect". Since this situation is the solely well-known contribution that he discussed incongruity of humorous expressions, several scholars have not given him credits, (ibid).

Incongruity resolutions may be manipulated to make humor. In this regard, Jenson (2009: 5) mentions three features of "incongruity-based humorous expressions" that are:

1. Conflict between what may predicted and what may state in the jokes.
2. Vagueness at some points of language which causes conflict.
3. Amazement at the ending of the jokes which triggers senses that are not estimated since they are not concordant or consistent with the rest of the jokes.

1.1.3 The Pragmatics and Racial Jokes

Richards and Schmidt (2010: 412) states that pragmatics is concerned with "the study of the use of language in communication, particularly the relationships between sentences and the contexts and situations in which they are used". However, the following points will illustrate racial jokes in terms of pragmatic issues.

- **Implicature**

For Hurford et al (2007: 67), implicature is "a concept of utterance meaning as opposed to sentence meaning". It is related to the method by which addressers work out the indirect illocutionary utterances. Yule (2010: 123) considers implicature as an additional sense conveyed by speakers adhering to the scope of co-operative principle. Cruse (2006: 58) adds that two basic kinds of implicature can be distinguished that are:

(a) Those which have stable associations with some linguistic expressions "conventional implicatures", such as the factor of surprise associated with *yet*, as in, "Haven't you finished yet?" (Speakers do not actually utter what they are surprised).

(b) Those which should be extracted, and for which contextual information is crucial (conversational implicature (CI), such as, the implied negative in B's reply in:

A: "Can I speak to Jane?"

B: "She's in the shower. Can you call back?"

Additionally, Finch (2005: 159) views that conventional implicature is not depended on the cooperative principle in its interpretation and it does not depend on a special context to be interpreted. It is

associated with specific words and result in additional conveyed meaning. Instances of such words are "but" which denotes contrast, "even" which denotes "contrary to the expectation" and "yet" sense the situation is different at a later time. For instance:

- "Some students passed the exam".

Consequently, the idea of "conversational implicature" can be viewed as one of the most crucial topics in pragmatics, comprehended due to the assumption that certain conversational maxims are respected. On this ground, Richard and Schmidt (2010: 67) argue that conversational maxim is an unwritten rule in relation to conversation which individuals know and influences the aspect of conversational exchanges. For instance, in the following exchange:

A: "Let's go to the movies".

B: "I have an examination in the morning".

B's response might seem not to be linked to A's remark. Because A has formed an invitation and because a reply to an invitation is normally either a refusal or an acceptance, B's reply is hence interpreted as an excuse for not accepting the invitation (i.e. a refusal). B has utilized the "maxim" that addressers normally give responses which are concerned with the question which has been questioned.

- **Grice's Maxims**

Ariel (2008) states that Gricean four maxims illustrate the application of cooperative principle. Such conversational maxims are:

1. Quantity refers to the quantity of information being provided and under which classify the following principles:

-Make your contribution as informative as is needed (for the present purpose of the exchange).

-Do not let your contribution more informative than is needed.

2. Quality: attempt to make your contribution one that is actually true.

-Do not mention what you believe being false.

-Do not mention that for which you lack adequate evidences.

3. Relation:

-Be relevant.

4. Manner: Be clear in your manner. It must do with how something should be uttered.

-Avoid ambiguous expressions.

-Avoid vagueness by all ways.

-Be short (avoid unnecessary prolixity).

-Create senses of order. (Grice, 1989: 27)

In any communication process, these maxims may be observed, violated, flouted or opted out. This determines how meanings should be understood. As speakers notice and obey the maxims of conversation, it would appear that it is easy for the hearer to make the suitable inferences that what is denoted is exactly of what is uttered. So, when one of the maxims is violated or flouted, the meanings of the sentences will not be interpreted as it is supposed being (intended). Thus, the cooperative principle is useful in figuring out and pointing the conversational implicature, (Bach, 2006: 78).

1.2 Methodology

The current study is associated with the pragmatic phenomena of racial jokes. The methodological method utilized in this study is predominantly qualitative in nature because of the international nature of the pragmatic phenomena explored in the study, i.e. implicature and Grice's maxims. It is regarded the major instrument of the qualitative analysis since he observes the data in terms of trigger mechanism, racial jokes can emerge within blended triggers, superiority-based triggers or incongruity resolution-based triggers. An eclectic model will be adopted based on Attardo and Raskin (2017)'s model and Grice's (1975) models. Thus, it will differentiate between blended triggers, superiority-based triggers and incongruity resolution triggers.

Pragmatics Analysis of Racial Jokes on Twitter

Figure (1): The

1.2.1 Analysis of Data and Discussion

A racial joke can be observed via figure below:

Figure (1) An Instance of Racial Joke

In this preceding joke, it has been noticed that there is a difference between white and black individuals as it is stated that black individuals lack behaviour and are not cultured. The poster of the joke above intends to express his/her emotions of superiority over the black individuals. Such behaviour is focused by Scruton (1986: 156) who presents that, "If people dislike being laughed at.... It is certainly because laughter lessens its object in the subject's eyes". The joke makes up of the set-up portion representing by "What do black people do before eating chocolate ice cream?" and the punchline portion representing by "They put on white gloves so they don't eat their hands".

This emphasizes the joke poster's disparaging of black ones. He apparently makes humorous because of their eating habits by offering how uncultivated black individuals are, that they could confuse their own hands and chocolate ice cream. At the same time the joke poster makes humorous because of the colour of their own skin linking it to chocolate ice cream. The joke poster communicates such implicature by means of violating the maxim of relevance. Additionally, the employment of racial jokes is useful in the sense that it serves as the mixture relations between social attitudes through the employment of such jokes. Another example:

Figure no. (2) An Instance of Racial Joke

Concerning the above tweet, it represents an apparent example of a racial joke triggered by "incongruity resolution". Such joke involves the set-up, i.e. "What does separate humans and monkeys?" and the punch-line parts, i.e. "Mediterranean Sea". The joke poster uses two inconsistency conceptions, i.e. "humans and monkeys" in the set-up portion, and "Mediterranean Sea" within the punch-line. Thus, the salient sense of the regarded joke is disused in favor of implication and unpredicted but contextually suitable one.

On this basis, the form of such joke forms a conflict between the interpretative sense realized by "humans and monkeys" and unpopular meaning represented by "Mediterranean Sea". So, the sense results in the understanding of this funny joke. It is worth mentioning that incongruity form associated with this joke accounts due to the presence of two clashing notions simultaneously or the misconnection between the actual utterance and predicted content, (Miller, 2009: 3). The implicature is given rise that "humans and monkeys" can be differentiated from "Mediterranean Sea". Thus, the joke poster communicates such implicature by means of violating the relevance maxim. Another example is below:

Figure no. (3) An Example of A Joke

It can be stated that this sort of racial joke is called blended trigger which makes connection for both incongruity resolution-based and superiority-based triggers. That is, the regarded kind of this joke involves the sense of both superiority and clash senses in the same time.

In the previous tweet there is a mixture of forms of racial joke. Concerning superiority-based triggers view, the joke maker, being a white individual, expresses his own feelings of superiority over the black ones. Again, this behaviour is affirmed by several scholars, like, (Jensen, 2009:8), who explain that "the superiority theory" does not solely point out the inclusion of shortages in others such as the form of humour but also illuminates the mixture of relationships between public associations and social perspectives in terms of the employment of jokes via a way that lets black followers sense inferior. With reference to "incongruity resolution-based trigger", the joke poster combines between two contradictory conceptions. To explicate, "the black people have five white things, i.e. hands, feet, eyes, teeth and owner although they have black skin". So, he forms the present joke relying on the clash between the distinguishable body parts of a black individual and her/his owner. To conclude, the mixture of the two triggers, i.e. "superiority and incongruity-resolution", makes a new type of racial joke named as blended based trigger. The concerned joke involves the set-up portion representing by "what are the five parts of black person", and the punch-line one which represents by "the black people have five white things, i.e. hands, feet, eyes, teeth, his owner".

1.2.2 Results

It has been found from the previous analysis that three types of racial jokes are identified. These were incongruity resolution-based triggers, superiority-based triggers and blended triggers. So, the former hypothesis is verified, i.e. three types of racial jokes can be distinguished, i.e. these were incongruity resolution-based triggers, superiority-based triggers and blended triggers. It has also been noticed that racial jokes involving incongruity are frequently used in online communication. Thus, the latter hypothesis is confirmed, i.e. most racial jokes are concerned with incongruity-based triggers.

Conclusions

The following points are worth mention:

1. The racial jokes are typically employed as effective devices of social effects, which enhance not solely scale within societies but also social orders. The feelings of social links is mostly reflected in terms of other individuals of the social associations, in which a special social status is stated.
2. Three humor theories can be distinguished, i.e. superiority, relief and incongruity-based triggers.
3. Gricean four maxims illustrate the application of cooperative principle. Such conversational maxims are: quantity, quality, relation and manner.
4. As for data analysis, three types of racial jokes are identified which are incongruity resolution-based triggers, superiority-based triggers and blended triggers. So, the former hypothesis is verified, i.e. three types of racial jokes can be distinguished, i.e. these were incongruity resolution-based triggers, superiority-based triggers and blended triggers. It has also been noticed that racial jokes involving the three preceding types are frequently used in online communication. Thus, the latter hypothesis is not confirmed, i.e. most racial jokes are concerned with incongruity-based triggers.

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